

ON THE FROBENIUS NUMBER OF FIBONACCI NUMERICAL SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract

In this note we investigate the Frobenius number of *Fibonacci numerical semigroups*, that is, numerical semigroups generated by a set of Fibonacci numbers.

1. Introduction

Let s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n be positive integers such that their greatest common divisor is one. Let $S = \langle s_1, \dots, s_n \rangle$ be the numerical semigroup¹ generated by s_1, \dots, s_n . A *Fibonacci numerical semigroup* is a numerical semigroup generated by a set of Fibonacci numbers F_{i_1}, \dots, F_{i_r} , for some integers $3 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_r$ where $\gcd(F_{i_1}, \dots, F_{i_r}) = 1$.

The so-called *Frobenius number*, denoted by $g(s_1, \dots, s_n)$, is defined as the largest integer not belonging to S , that is, the largest integer that is not representable as a nonnegative integer combination of s_1, \dots, s_n . It is well known that $g(s_1, s_2) = s_1 s_2 - s_1 - s_2$. In general, finding $g(S)$ is a difficult problem and so formulas and upper bounds for particular sequences are of interest. For instance, it is known [3] $g(S)$ when S is an arithmetical sequence

$$g(a, a + d, \dots, a + kd) = a \left(\left\lfloor \frac{a-2}{k} \right\rfloor \right) + d(a-1) \quad (1)$$

¹Recall that a *semigroup* $(S, *)$ consists of a nonempty set S and an associative binary operation $*$ on S . If, in addition, there exists an element, which is usually denoted by 0, in S such that $a + 0 = 0 + a = a$ for all $a \in S$, we say that $(S, *)$ is a *monoid*. A *numerical semigroup* is a submonoid of \mathbb{N} such that the greatest common divisor of its elements is equal to one.

We refer the reader to [2] where a complete account on the Frobenius problem can be found.

In this note, we investigate the value of $g(F_i, F_j, F_l)$ for some triples $3 \leq i < j < l$ (we always assume that $\gcd(F_i, F_j, F_l) = 1$; recall that $\gcd(F_i, F_{i+l}) = 1$ if $i \nmid l$).

We first notice that $g(F_i, F_{i+1}, F_l) = g(F_i, F_{i+1})$ for any integer $l \geq i + 2$. Indeed, since $F_l = F_{i+m} = F_m F_{i+1} + F_{m-1} F_i$ is a nonnegative integer combination of F_i and F_{i+1} then the semigroups $\langle F_i, F_{i+1}, F_l \rangle$ and $\langle F_i, F_{i+1} \rangle$ generate the same set of elements and thus they have the same Frobenius number.

Let us consider then $g(F_i, F_{i+2}, F_l)$ with $l \geq i + 3$. We notice that the case when $l = i + 3$ is a consequence of equation (1) since the triple $\{F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+3}\} = \{F_i, F_i + F_{i+1}, F_i + 2F_{i+1}\}$ form an arithmetical sequence. However, it can be checked that $\{F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+k}\}$ do not form an arithmetical sequence when $k \geq 3$ and the calculation of $g(F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+k})$ is more complicated.

We state our main result.

Theorem 1. *Let $i, k \geq 3$ be integers and let $r = \lfloor \frac{F_i-1}{F_k} \rfloor$. Then,*

$$g(F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+k}) = \begin{cases} (F_i - 1)F_{i+2} - F_i(rF_{k-2} + 1) & \text{if } r = 0 \text{ or } r \geq 1 \text{ and} \\ & F_{k-2}F_i < (F_i - rF_k)F_{i+2}, \\ (rF_k - 1)F_{i+2} - F_i((r - 1)F_{k-2} + 1) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $N(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ be the number of positive integers with no representation by a non-negative integer combination of a_1, \dots, a_n . Theorem 1 yields to the following result.

Corollary 2. *Let $i, k \geq 3$ be integers and let $r = \lfloor \frac{F_i-1}{F_k} \rfloor$. Then,*

$$N(F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+k}) = \frac{(F_i - 1)(F_{i+2} - 1) - rF_{k-2}(2F_i - F_k(1 + r))}{2}.$$

2. Fibonacci semigroups

In order to prove Theorem 1 we need the following result due to Brauer and Shockley [1].

Lemma 3. *Let $1 < a_1 < \dots < a_n$ be integers with $\gcd(a_1, \dots, a_n) = 1$. Then,*

$$g(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \max_{l \in \{1, 2, \dots, a_n-1\}} \{t_l\} - a_1,$$

where t_l is the smallest positive integer congruent to l modulo a_1 , that is representable as a nonnegative integer combination of a_2, \dots, a_n .

Proof. Let L be a positive integer. If $L \equiv 0 \pmod{a_1}$ then L is a nonnegative integer combination of a_1 . If $L \equiv l \pmod{a_1}$ then L is a nonnegative integer combination of a_1, \dots, a_n if and only if $L \geq t_l$. □

Let $T^* = \{t_0^*, \dots, t_{F_i-1}^*\}$ where t_l^* is the smallest positive integer congruent to l modulo F_i , that is representable as a nonnegative integer combination of F_{i+2} and F_{i+k} . By Lemma 3, it suffices to find t_l^* for each $l = 0, 1, \dots, F_i - 1$. To this end, we consider all nonnegative integer combinations of F_{i+2} and F_{i+k} . We construct the following table, denoted by T_1 , having as entry $t_{x,y}$ the combination of the form $x F_{i+2} + y F_{i+k}$ with integers $x, y \geq 0$, see below.

$x \backslash y$	0	1	2	...
0	0	F_{i+k}	$2F_{i+k}$...
1	F_{i+2}	$F_{i+k} + F_{i+2}$	$2F_{i+k} + F_{i+2}$...
2	$2F_{i+2}$	$F_{i+k} + 2F_{i+2}$	$2F_{i+k} + 2F_{i+2}$...
3	$3F_{i+2}$	$F_{i+k} + 3F_{i+2}$	$2F_{i+k} + 3F_{i+2}$...
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
$F_k - 1$	$(F_k - 1)F_{i+2}$	$F_{i+k} + (F_k - 1)F_{i+2}$	$2F_{i+k} + (F_k - 1)F_{i+2}$...
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

We notice that

$$F_{i+k} = F_{k-2}F_{i+1} + F_{k-1}F_{i+2} = F_{k-2}(F_{i+2} - F_i) + F_{k-1}F_{i+2} = F_{i+2}F_k - F_{k-2}F_i$$

so, we obtain that

$$x F_{i+2} + y F_{i+k} = x F_{i+2} + y(F_{i+2}F_k - F_{k-2}F_i) = (x + y F_k)F_{i+2} - y F_{k-2}F_i.$$

Thus, T_1 can also be given by the following table, denoted by T_2 ,

$x \backslash y$	0	1	2	...	r	...
0	0	$F_k F_{i+2} - F_{k-2} F_i$	$2F_k F_{i+2} - 2F_{k-2} F_i$...	$r F_k F_{i+2} - r F_{k-2} F_i$...
1	F_{i+2}	$(1 + F_k)F_{i+2} - F_{k-2} F_i$	$(1 + 2F_k)F_{i+2} - 2F_{k-2} F_i$...	$(1 + r F_k)F_{i+2} - r F_{k-2} F_i$...
2	$2F_{i+2}$	$(2 + F_k)F_{i+2} - F_{k-2} F_i$	$(2 + 2F_k)F_{i+2} - 2F_{k-2} F_i$...	$(2 + r F_k)F_{i+2} - r F_{k-2} F_i$...
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
l	$l F_{i+2}$	$(l + F_k)F_{i+2} - F_{k-2} F_i$	$(l + 2F_k)F_{i+2} - 2F_{k-2} F_i$...	$(l + r F_k)F_{i+2} - r F_{k-2} F_i$...
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
$F_k - 1$	$(F_k - 1)F_{i+2}$	$(2F_k - 1)F_{i+2} - F_{k-2} F_i$	$(3F_k - 1)F_{i+2} - 2F_{k-2} F_i$
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

Let S be the set formed by the first $F_k - 1$ entries of columns zero, one, two, and so on, that is, $S = \{t_{0,0}, t_{1,0}, \dots, t_{F_k-1,0}, t_{0,1}, t_{1,1}, \dots, t_{F_k-1,1}, \dots, t_{0,r}, t_{1,r}, \dots, t_{F_k-1,r}, \dots\}$.

Remark 4.

(a) Let $r = \lfloor \frac{F_i-1}{F_k} \rfloor$ and set $F_i - 1 = rF_k + l$ for some integer $0 \leq l \leq F_k - 1$. Let

$$S' = \{t_{0,0}, t_{1,0}, \dots, t_{F_k-1,0}, t_{0,1}, t_{1,1}, \dots, t_{F_k-1,1}, \dots, t_{2,r}, t_{1,r}, \dots, t_{l,r}\},$$

Then, for each $t_{x,y} = (x + yF_k)F_{i+2} - yF_{k-2}F_i \in S'$ we have that $0 \leq x + yF_k \leq F_i - 1$. Moreover, since $\gcd(F_{i+2}, F_i) = 1$ then S' forms a complete system of rests modulo F_i .

(b) The elements of S can be represented as $s_x = xF_{i+2} - \lfloor \frac{x}{F_k} \rfloor F_{k-2}F_i$ for $x = 0, 1, \dots$. Indeed, it can be checked that $S = \bigcup_{q \geq 1} S_q$ where

$$S_q = \{s_{qF_k}, s_{qF_k+1}, \dots, s_{(q+1)F_k-1}\} = \{t_{0,q}, \dots, t_{F_k-1,q}\}$$

for each integer $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

(c) By using table T_2 we have that $t_{i,j} < t_{k,l}$ for all $i \leq k$ and all $j \leq l$.

Lemma 5. Let $t_{u,v}$ be an entry of T_1 such that $t_{u,v} \notin S'$. Then, there exists $t_{x,y} \in S'$ such that $t_{u,v} \equiv t_{x,y} \pmod{F_i}$ and $t_{u,v} > t_{x,y}$.

Proof. We first notice that the set S can be written as follows

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{cccccccccccc} s_0, & \dots, & s_{F_k-1}, & s_{F_k}, & \dots, & s_{2F_k-1}, & \dots, & s_{rF_k}, & \dots, & s_{rF_k+l} = s_{F_i-1}, \\ s_{F_i}, & \dots, & s_{F_i+F_k-1}, & s_{F_i+F_k}, & \dots, & s_{F_i+2F_k-1}, & \dots, & s_{F_i+rF_k}, & \dots, & s_{2F_i-1}, \\ s_{2F_i}, & \dots, & s_{2F_i+F_k-1}, & s_{2F_i+F_k}, & \dots, & s_{2F_i+2F_k-1}, & \dots, & s_{2F_i+rF_k}, & \dots, & s_{3F_i-1}, \dots \end{array} \right\}$$

where $S' = \{s_0, \dots, s_{F_k-1}, s_{F_k}, \dots, s_{2F_k-1}, \dots, s_{rF_k}, \dots, s_{F_i-1}\}$. We have two cases.

Case A. Suppose that $t_{u,v} \in S \setminus S'$. Then $t_{u,v}$ is of the form s_{pF_i+g} for some integers $p \geq 1$ and $0 \leq g \leq F_i - 1$. It is clear that,

$$s_g = gF_{i+2} - \left\lfloor \frac{g}{F_k} \right\rfloor F_i F_{k-2} \equiv (pF_i + g)F_{i+2} - \left\lfloor \frac{pF_i + g}{F_k} \right\rfloor F_i F_{k-2} = g_{pF_i+g} \pmod{F_i}.$$

We will show that $s_{pF_i+g} > s_g$. To this end, it suffices to prove that $s_{F_i+g} > s_g$ (since $s_{pF_i+g} \geq s_{F_i+g}$). Recall that $r = \lfloor \frac{F_i-1}{F_k} \rfloor$ and that $F_i - 1 = rF_k + l$ for some integer $0 \leq l \leq F_k - 1$. We have two subcases.

Subcase a. If $r = 0$ then $F_k \geq F_i$. If $F_k = F_i$ then $s_{F_i+g} = t_{g,1}$ and, by Remark 4(c), $t_{g,0} < t_{g,1}$. If $F_k > F_i$ then $s_{F_i+g} = t_{q,0}$ for some integer $q \geq F_i$ and, by Remark 4(c), $t_{g,0} < t_{q,0}$.

Subcase b. If $r \geq 1$, then $s_{F_i+g} > s_g$ holds if and only if

$$(F_i + g)F_{i+2} - \left\lfloor \frac{F_i + g}{F_k} \right\rfloor F_i F_{k-2} > gF_{i+2} - \left\lfloor \frac{g}{F_k} \right\rfloor F_i F_{k-2}$$

or equivalently if and only if

$$F_{i+2} > F_{k-2} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{F_i + g}{F_k} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{g}{F_k} \right\rfloor \right).$$

Let $g = mF_k + n$ with $0 \leq n \leq F_k - 1$. Since $F_i - 1 = rF_k + l$ with $0 \leq l \leq F_k - 1$, then

$$\left\lfloor \frac{F_i - 1 + g + 1}{F_k} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{rF_k + l + mF_k + n + 1}{F_k} \right\rfloor \leq r + m + 1$$

and thus

$$\left\lfloor \frac{F_i + g}{F_k} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{g}{F_k} \right\rfloor \leq r + m + 1 - m = r + 1.$$

So, it is enough to show that $F_{i+2} > (r + 1)F_{k-2}$ or equivalently to show that $F_i + F_{i+1} > (r + 1)F_{k-2}$. Since $F_i = rF_k + l + 1$ then the latter inequality holds if and only if $rF_k + l + 1 + F_{i+1} > rF_{k-2} + F_{k-2}$, that is, if and only if

$$r(F_k - F_{k-2}) + l + 1 + F_{i+1} = r(F_{k-1}) + l + 1 + F_{i+1} > F_{k-2}$$

which is true since $r \geq 1$.

Case B. Suppose that $t_{u,v} \notin S$. Then we have that $0 \leq x \leq F_k - 1 < u$. If $v \geq y$ then, by Remark 4(c), $t_{x,y} < t_{x,v} < t_{u,v}$. So, we suppose that $v < y$. Since, $t_{u,v} \equiv t_{x,y} \pmod{F_i}$ then $u + vF_k \equiv x + yF_k \pmod{F_i}$ but, by Remark 4(a), $0 \leq x + yF_k \leq F_i - 1$ so $u + vF_k = d(x + yF_k)$ for some integer $d \geq 1$ and thus $u + vF_k \geq x + yF_k$. Also, since $v < y$, then $-vF_{k-2}F_i > -yF_{k-2}F_i$. So, combining the last two inequalities we have that

$$t_{u,v} = (u + vF_k)F_{i+2} - vF_{k-2}F_i > (x + yF_k)F_{i+2} - yF_{k-2}F_i = t_{x,y}.$$

□

We may now prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let $T^* = \{t_0^*, \dots, t_{F_i-1}^*\}$ where t_l^* is the smallest positive integer congruent to l modulo F_i , that is representable as a nonnegative integer combination of F_{i+2} and F_{i+k} . Let $s_x = xF_{i+2} - \lfloor \frac{x}{F_k} \rfloor F_{k-2}F_i$ for $x = 0, 1, \dots$. By Lemma 5, we have that for each $x = 0, \dots, F_i - 1$, s_x is the smallest positive integer congruent to l modulo F_i , for some integer $0 \leq l \leq F_i - 1$, that is representable as a nonnegative integer combination of F_{i+2} and F_{i+k} , that is, $S' = T^*$ where $S' = \{s_0, \dots, s_{F_k-1}, s_{F_k}, \dots, s_{2F_k-1}, \dots, s_{rF_k}, \dots, s_{F_i-1}\}$. Now, by Remark 4(c), if $r \geq 1$ then

$$t_{F_k-1,i} = \max_{0 \leq x \leq F_k-1} \{t_{x,i} | t_{x,i} \in S'\} \text{ for each } i = 0, \dots, r - 1,$$

$$t_{F_k-1,r-1} = \max_{0 \leq i \leq r-1} \{t_{F_k-1,i} | t_{F_k-1,i} \in S'\},$$

and

$$t_{l,r} = \max_{0 \leq x \leq l} \{t_{x,r} | t_{x,r} \in S'\}.$$

Thus,

$$\max\{s | s \in S'\} = \begin{cases} t_{l,r} & \text{if } r = 0, \\ \max\{t_{F_k-1,r-1}, t_{l,r}\} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The result follows since $t_{l,r} > t_{F_k-1,r-1}$ if and only if

$$(rF_k + l)F_{i+2} - rF_{k-2}F_i = (F_i - 1)F_{i+2} - rF_{k-2}F_i > (rF_k - 1)F_{i+2} - (r - 1)F_{k-2}F_i$$

or equivalently, if and only if $F_{i+2}(F_i - rF_k) > F_{k-2}F_i$. □

We will use the following result due to Selmer [4] to show Corollary 2.

Lemma 6. *Let $1 < a_1 < \dots < a_n$ be integers with $\gcd(a_1, \dots, a_n) = 1$. If $L = \{1, \dots, a_1 - 1\}$ then $N(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \frac{1}{a_1} \sum_{l \in L} t_l - \frac{a_1 - 1}{2}$, where t_l is the smallest positive integer congruent to l modulo a_1 , that is representable as a nonnegative integer combination of a_2, \dots, a_n .*

Proof. The number of $M \equiv l \not\equiv 0 \pmod{a_1}$ with $0 < M < t_l$ is given by $\lfloor \frac{t_l}{a_1} \rfloor$. By assuming that $0 < l < a_1$, we have $\lfloor \frac{t_l}{a_1} \rfloor = \frac{t_l - l}{a_1}$. The result follows by summing over $l \in L$. □

Proof of Corollary 2. Let $r = \lfloor \frac{F_i - 1}{F_k} \rfloor$ and set $F_i - 1 = rF_k + l$ for some integer $0 \leq l \leq F_k - 1$. By Lemma 6 and Remark 4(b), we have

$$\begin{aligned} N(F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+k}) &= \frac{1}{F_i} \sum_{s \in S'} s - \frac{F_i - 1}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{F_i} \sum_{j=0}^{F_i - 1} (jF_{i+2} - F_{k-2} \lfloor \frac{j}{F_k} \rfloor F_i) - \frac{F_i - 1}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{F_i} \left(F_{i+2} \frac{(F_i - 1)F_i}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{F_i} (F_{k-2} F_i) \sum_{j=0}^{F_i - 1} \lfloor \frac{j}{F_k} \rfloor - \frac{F_i - 1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

By using the table T_1 , it is easy to verify that

$$\sum_{j=0}^{F_i - 1} \lfloor \frac{j}{F_k} \rfloor = 0 + F_k + 2F_k + \dots + (r - 1)F_k + r(l + 1) = \frac{F_k(r - 1)r}{2} + r(l + 1)$$

and, since $l + 1 = F_i - rF_k$, that

$$\begin{aligned} N(F_i, F_{i+2}, F_{i+k}) &= \frac{F_{i+2}(F_i - 1)}{2} - F_{k-2} \left(\frac{F_k(r - 1)r}{2} + r(F_i - rF_k) \right) - \frac{F_i - 1}{2} \\ &= \frac{(F_i - 1)(F_{i+2} - 1)}{2} - F_{k-2} \left(\frac{F_k r^2 - F_k r + 2F_i r - 2r^2 F_k}{2} \right) \\ &= \frac{(F_i - 1)(F_{i+2} - 1) - rF_{k-2}(2F_i - F_k(1 + r))}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

□

We end with the following problem.

Problem. Find upper (and lower) bounds (or formulas) for $g(F_i, F_j, F_k)$ for further triples $3 \leq i < j < k$.

References

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